

Studies in Tetraphenylmethane Derivatives : Non-quinonoid Dyes. Part I.

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A careful perusal of the literature shows that the few tetraphenylmethane derivatives known at present were obtained mostly as by-products in some complicated reactions (Mackenzie, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, **79**, 1209; Gomberg and Berger, *Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 1088; Copisarow, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **111**, 10; Ramm and Schmajewaki, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1921, **4**, 538), though a few attempts at the direct synthesis of simple derivatives are also recorded (Baeyer and Villiger, *Ber.*, 1902, **35**, 3013; Ullmann and Münzhuber, *Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 404; Boyd and Hardy, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, p. 630, published when this work was in progress). In most of these cases, the derivatives were obtained in such poor yields as to be of little value in their systematic study. Further these derivatives are either mono-substituted (Baeyer and Villiger, *loc. cit.*, Ullmann and Münzhuber, *loc. cit.*) or di-substituted (Mackenzie, *loc. cit.*, Zincke and Wugk, *Annalen*, 1908, **363**, 284; Rassow, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1901, *ii*, **64**, 129) a few tri-substituted derivatives being also known (Zincke and Wugk, *loc. cit.*) with substitutions in not more than two nuclei.

The present work has been undertaken with a view to prepare tetraphenylmethane derivatives substituted in all the four nuclei and study their characteristics. The method, which has been found most convenient for this purpose, is to condense a triphenylcarbinol substituted in each of the three benzene nuclei with suitable mono-, di-, tri-, or tetra-substituted benzene derivatives, the condensation being effected by heating to 150—170° in the presence of freshly fused anhydrous sodium acetate. The reaction which takes place may be represented as follows :

As usual the hydrogen atom, in the *para*-position to the substituting group in the benzene derivatives, reacting with the OH-group of the carbinol, the condensation taking place in the *ortho*-position as well

when the *para*-position is occupied (as in the condensation of rosaniline base and *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid). This method is somewhat similar to that used by Baeyer and Villiger (*loc. cit.*) for the preparation of hydroxytetraphenylmethane and also by Ullmann and Münzhuber (*loc. cit.*) for the preparation of aminotetraphenylmethane and gives a very satisfactory yield (60 to 80 per cent.).

These tetraphenylmethane derivatives, substituted in all the four nuclei by NH_2 - and OH-groups (with other groups in addition in some cases) are interesting not only because they have been prepared now for the first time but also on account of the remarkable observation that they are all more or less deeply coloured compounds and possess satisfactory dyeing properties, the amino-compounds, in general, producing on wool and silk, beautiful reddish to bluish-violet shades and the hydroxy-compounds yellow to pinkish shades.

It is evident from the structure of these compounds that they do not contain the so-called chromophores nor do they admit of any quinonoid configuration according to the accepted modes of tautomerisation and yet they are as good dyes as the triphenylcarbinol compounds, the colour and dyeing properties of which are generally attributed to their quinonoid transformation on salt formation. This appearance of colour and dyeing properties in compounds apparently devoid of the so-called chromophores may be accounted for by assuming that tetraphenylmethane itself is a colourless chromogen (like triphenylcarbinol) in which visible colour is developed (*i.e.*, the absorption band in the ultra-violet region is shifted into the visible part of the spectrum) by the introduction of suitable auxochromes into the various benzene nuclei. Similar tetraphenylmethane compounds with a pyrone ring possessing colour and marked dyeing properties have been previously described by Sen, Chattopadhyay and Sen-Gupta (*J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 997) which also do not admit of any quinonoid configuration.

The following table gives a comparative study of the influence of different auxochromes on the colour and dyeing properties of the compounds described in the paper.

TABLE I.

No.	Compound (R=rosaniline base).	Colour and dyeing properties.	Remarks.
I.	$C(C_6H_4 \cdot NH_2)_4$ (from R + aniline)	A delightful bluish-violet shade.	Contains one NH_2 -group in each of the four benzene nuclei.
	$C(C_6H_4 \cdot NH \cdot CH_3)_4$ by methylation of (I)	Bluer shade.	Alkylation of NH_2 -groups, as in the triphenylmethane dyes, strengthens the auxochrome.*
II.	$(CH_3)_2NC_6H_4 \cdot C(C_6H_4 \cdot NH_2)_3$ (from R + dimethyl-aniline).	Slightly redder shade.	Effect of alkylation not very marked, the colour not being deepened.
III.	$AcNH \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot C(C_6H_4 \cdot NH_2)_3$ (from R + acetanilide).	Brownish-grey shade.	Acetylation of NH_2 -groups weakens the auxochrome as usual.
	$C(C_6H_4 \cdot NHAc)_4$ by acetylation of (I)	Slightly coloured; no dyeing property.	
	$C(C_6H_4 \cdot NH \cdot CO \cdot C_6H_5)_4$ by benzoylation of (I)	Only a violet tinge.	Benzoylation of NH_2 -groups also weakens the auxochrome.
IV.	$OH \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot C(C_6H_4 \cdot NH_2)_3$ (from R + phenol)	Light reddish-violet shade. (The affinity for the fibre is markedly impaired due to the presence of the acidic OH group in a basic dye.)	When a stronger auxochrome such as NH_2 is replaced by a weaker auxochrome, OH, there is generally a corresponding weakening of colour according as one or more NH_2 -groups are replaced by OH.
V.	$CH_3O \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot C(C_6H_4 \cdot NH_2)_3$ (from R + anisole)	Shade much lighter than (I).	The affinity for the fibre is greater than that produced by (IV). Shade is lighter than (I) as one of the auxochromes is eliminated.

* Such slight anomalies are also noticed in the triphenylcarbinol dyes; for instance diaminotriphenylcarbinol gives a violet dye (Döbner's violet, while triaminotriphenylcarbinol gives a red dye rosaniline; tetramethyldiaminotriphenylcarbinol gives a green dye, malachite green while hexamethyltriaminotriphenylcarbinol gives a violet dye, crystal violet.

TABLE I—(contd.)

No.	Compound (R = Rosaniline base).	Colour and dyeing properties.	Remarks.
VI.	$(OH)_2 \cdot C_6H_3 \cdot C(C_6H_4NH_2)_3$ (from R + resorcinol)	Reddish-violet shade.	Much better dye than (IV).
VII.	$(OH)_3 \cdot C_6H_2 \cdot C(C_6H_4NH_2)_3$ (from R + pyrogallol)	„	„
VIII-X.	$(OH)(COOH) \cdot C_6H_3 \cdot C(C_6H_4NH_2)_3$ (from R + salicylic acid, <i>p</i> -hydroxybenzoic acid), or <i>m</i> -hydroxybenzoic acid).	Much deeper shade (bluer)	The carboxy group exerts a remarkable influence in augmenting the depth of colour, stronger effect being produced with the CO_2H group in <i>ortho</i> -position.
XI.	$(OH)(CO_2H)C_6H_2(Me) \cdot C(C_6H_4NH_2)_3$ (from R + <i>o</i> -cresotinic acid)	Beautiful violet shade; (much bluer than (VIII).	Effect of the CH_3 group.
XII.	$(OH)_3(CO_2H) \cdot C_6H \cdot C(C_6H_4NH_2)_3$ (from R + gallic acid)	Slightly redder than (VII).	Effect of the CO_2H group on trihydroxytriaminotetra-phenylmethane is not very marked.
Tri-, tetra-, penta-, hexa-hydroxy-derivatives (obtained from II, III, IV, I, VI and VIII by diazo reaction).		Very light shades of yellow to pink.	A minimum of three hydroxyl groups in three different nuclei being required for the development of yellow colour.

From the above table it is evident that the amino-compounds are better dyes than the hydroxy-compounds, a minimum of three auxochromes being required in either case for the development of fairly deep colour and dyeing property.

Two very interesting observations have also been made in the case of the amino-compounds in general (having at least three NH_2 groups). (a) The colour in strong mineral acid solution undergoes a remarkable change on dilution.* (b) Different dye shades on wool and silk are produced according as the dyeing takes place from an acetic acid or a mineral acid bath; the shades in the latter case being bluer. The hydroxy-compounds have also an interesting property, their solutions in caustic alkalis and ammonia exhibiting slight fluorescence.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Symmetrical p-Tetra-aminotetraphenylmethane, $\text{C}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{NH}_2)_4$. —*p*-Rosaniline base (2.5 g.), freshly distilled aniline (5 g.) and fused sodium acetate (10 g.) are heated together at 160° for 8 hours. The excess of aniline is distilled off in steam and the product extracted with 5*N*-hydrochloric acid. The acid solution is filtered and made alkaline with ammonia. The precipitate is filtered off and washed with boiling water and dried. The powdered mass is then washed with boiling chloroform and ether and then crystallised from alcohol in shining violet-black leaflets (not melting up to 280°), soluble in alcohol, acetone, mineral acids (bluish-violet solution), and acetic acid (reddish-violet solution) and insoluble in chloroform, benzene, and ether. The acetic acid solution dyes wool and silk bluish-violet, while mineral acid solutions dye a much bluer shade. Yield 70%. (Found: N, 14.06. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4$ requires N, 14.74 per cent.)

The *tetramethyl* derivative was prepared by methylating the above compound. It crystallised from alcohol as fine shining micro-crystalline powder, soluble in acetone, alcohol (reddish-violet solution), acetic acid (bluish-violet solution), mineral acids (greenish-blue solution), and insoluble in ether, benzene and chloroform. It dyes wool and silk a light blue shade from acetic acid bath. The affinity for fibre is rather weak. Yield 70%. (Found:

* A strong acid solution of $\text{C}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{NH}_2)_4$ is greenish-yellow which on dilution changes to bluish-violet; the strong acid solution of $\text{Me}_2\text{N}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{C}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{NH}_2)_3$ is blue which on dilution changes to deep bluish-violet.

C, 79.5 ; H, 7.6 ; N, 12.6. $C_{29}H_{32}N_4$ requires C, 79.81 ; H, 7.34 ; N, 12.84 per cent.)

The *monoacetyl* derivative was prepared by condensing *p*-rosaniline base and acetanilide at 150° for 8 hours, subsequent operations being same as in (I) (yield 60%). It formed greyish-violet micro-crystalline powder (not melting up to 250°), sparingly soluble in absolute alcohol, fairly soluble in acetic acid ; insoluble in benzene, ether and chloroform. The acetic acid solution dyes wool and silk brownish-grey. (Found : N, 12.96. $C_{27}H_{26}ON_4$ requires N, 13.22 per cent.)

The *sym.-tetra-acetyl* derivative was prepared from (I) by acetylation, and formed dark grey powder, m.p. 218° (decomp.) soluble in glacial acetic acid, having no tinctorial property. (Found : N, 10.71. $C_{33}H_{32}O_4N_4$ requires N, 10.2 per cent.)

The *sym.-tetrabenzoyl* derivative was prepared by benzoylating (I). It is almost colourless and has no tinctorial property. (Found : N, 6.5. $C_{53}H_{40}O_4N_4$ requires N, 7.04 per cent.)

A *dimethyl* derivative (II) was prepared by condensing *p*-rosaniline base with dimethylaniline as in (I). It formed greyish-violet micro-crystalline powder (not melting up to 280°, soluble in alcohol, acetic acid and acetone ; insoluble in benzene, chloroform, and ether. The acetic acid bath dyes wool and silk a beautiful reddish-violet shade (yield 70%). (Found : N, 14.05. $C_{27}H_{28}N_4$ requires N, 13.72 per cent.)

Tri-p-hydroxy-p-dimethylaminotetraphenylmethane.—It was prepared by diazotizing a hot acetic acid solution of the above dimethyl compound with sodium nitrite in the usual manner. The precipitated hydroxy-compound is filtered, dissolved in a freshly prepared solution of caustic soda and reprecipitated with an excess of 5N-sulphuric acid, again filtered, dried and crystallised from alcohol as dark-brown microcrystalline powder (not melting up to 250°) soluble in caustic alkalis and ammonia giving slightly fluorescent solution and sparingly soluble in absolute alcohol. The ammonium salt solution dyes wool and silk light turmeric yellow shades (yield 80%). (Found : N, 3.1. $C_{27}H_{25}O_3N$ requires N, 3.4 per cent.)

p-Hydroxytri-p-aminotetraphenylmethane (IV) was prepared by condensing phenol (carefully dried in a desiccator) and *p*-rosaniline base for 6 hours at 150°. The subsequent operations are same as in (I) (yield 60%). It is a greyish-violet microcrystalline powder, melts at 170° (decom.) sparingly soluble in dilute mineral acids, freely in glacial acetic acid, also soluble in alcohol, acetone and

dilute caustic alkalis (to some extent on warming) ; insoluble in chloroform, ether and benzene. Its affinity for fibre is very weak; the acetic acid solution dyes wool and silk a light reddish-violet shade. (Found: N, 10·3. $C_{25}H_{23}ON_3$ requires N, 11·02 per cent.)

p-Methoxytri-p-aminotetraphenylmethane (V) was prepared by condensing *p*-rosaniline base and anisole as in the above case (yield 60%). It is a greyish-violet microcrystalline powder (not melting up to 260°), soluble in alcohol acetone, mineral acids and acetic acid (reddish-violet solution) ; insoluble in ether, benzene and chloroform. The acetic acid bath dyes wool and silk a dull reddish-violet shade. (Found: N, 10·34. $C_{26}H_{25}ON_3$ requires N, 10·63 per cent.)

p-Methoxytri-p-hydroxytetraphenylmethane was prepared from (V) by the diazo reaction (yield 80%). It is a shining grey powder (not melting up to 250°) soluble in caustic alkalis, ammonia and absolute alcohol, insoluble in acids, benzene, ether and chloroform. The ammonium salt solution dyes wool and silk a light yellow shade. (Found: C, 78·0 ; H, 5·9. $C_{26}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 78·4; H, 5·53 per cent.)

p-Tetrahydroxytetraphenylmethane was prepared from (I) by the diazo reaction (yield 80 per cent.). It formed shining dark brown leaflets (not melting up to 260°), soluble in alkalis and ammonia with slight fluorescence and also in alcohol, insoluble in acids, ether, and benzene. The ammonium salt solution dyes wool and silk a decent light-yellow shade. (Found: C, 77·9; H, 6·9. $C_{25}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 78·12; H, 6·67 per cent.)

Tetra-silver salt was prepared by adding silver nitrate to the cold ammonium salt solution. The precipitated is allowed to settle in the dark, then quickly filtered and dried in a vacuum desiccator kept also in a dark chamber. (Found: Ag 52·7. $C_{25}H_{16}O_4Ag_2$ requires Ag, 53·2 per cent.)

Tri-p hydroxy-p-acetylamino-tetraphenylmethane was prepared from the mono-acetyl derivative of (I) by the diazo reaction (yield 70 per cent.). The ammonium salt solution dyes wool and silk a light pinkish-yellow shade. (Found: N, 3·1. $C_{27}H_{23}O_4N$ requires N, 3·3 per cent.)

Tri-p-amino-2:4-dihydroxytetraphenylmethane (VI).—It was prepared by condensing resorcinol and *p*-rosaniline base at 155° for 8 hours. The excess of resorcinol is removed by boiling water. It is crystallised from alcohol as violet micro-crystalline powder, m.p.

160° (decomp.), soluble in alcohol, acetic acid and dilute mineral acids; slightly soluble in acetone, insoluble in water, ether, benzene and chloroform. The acetic acid solution dyes wool and silk a reddish-violet shade; while mineral acid bath gives a light bluish-violet shade (yield 60 per cent.). (Found: N, 9.96. $C_{25}H_{23}O_2N_3$ requires N, 10.58 per cent.)

Tri-p-hydroxy-2:4-dihydroxytetraphenylmethane was prepared from (VI) (yield 80 per cent.). It formed reddish-brown leaflets, (not melting up to 250°) soluble in caustic soda (deep orange-red solution with slight fluorescence), in ammonia (slightly fluorescent) and in absolute alcohol; insoluble in acids, ether, benzene and chloroform. The ammonium salt solution dyes wool and silk a pinkish shade. (Found: C, 74.3; H, 4.5. $C_{25}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 75.00; H, 4.00 per cent.)

Penta-silver Salt.—(Found: Ag, 57.6. $C_{25}H_{15}O_5Ag_5$ requires Ag, 57.75 per cent.)

Tri-p-amino(2:3:4)-trihydroxytetraphenylmethane (VII) was prepared by condensing pyrogallol and *p*-rosaniline base at 166° (yield 80 per cent.). It is a dark violet micro-crystalline powder, (not melting up to 260°), fairly soluble in hot dilute mineral acids and glacial acetic acid; sparingly soluble in alcohol. Dyes wool and silk a bluish-violet shade from an acetic acid bath. The dyeing affinity is weak. (Found: N, 10.5. $C_{25}H_{23}O_3N_3$ requires N, 10.17 per cent.)

Tri-p-hydroxy-2:3:4-trihydroxytetraphenylmethane was prepared from (VII) (yield 70 per cent.). (Found: C, 71.8; H, 5.00. $C_{25}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 72.1; H, 4.80 per cent.)

Hexa-silver Salt.—(Found: Ag, 60.12. $C_{25}H_{14}O_6Ag_6$ requires Ag, 61.2 per cent.)

Tri-p-amino-p-hydroxytetraphenylmethane-m-carboxylic acid (VIII) was obtained by condensing *p*-rosaniline base and salicylic acid at 150°, subsequent operations being same as in (VI) (yield 70 per cent.). It formed violet micro-crystalline powder (not melting up to 260°). Acetic Acid bath dyes reddish-violet while mineral acid bath dyes bluish-violet shades. It gives a slight effervescence with a dilute alcoholic solution of sodium bicarbonate. (Found: N, 9.75. $C_{26}H_{23}O_3N_3$ requires N, 9.9 per cent.)

Tetra-p-hydroxytetraphenylmethane-m-carboxylic Acid.—It was prepared from (VIII) as usual (yield 60 per cent.). It is a brownish micro-crystalline powder (not melting up to 260°).

soluble in caustic alkalis and ammonia (slight fluorescence) and absolute alcohol; insoluble in ether, benzene and chloroform; it effervesces slightly with a dilute alcoholic solution of sodium bicarbonate. The ammonium salt solution dyes wool and silk a light yellow shade. (Found: C, 72.7; H, 4.8. $C_{26}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 72.9; H, 4.6 per cent.)

Tri-p-amino-p-hydroxytetraphenylmethane-o-carboxylic acid (IX) was prepared by condensing *p*-rosaniline base and *m*-hydroxybenzoic acid at 170° (yield 70 per cent.). It is a dark violet microcrystalline powder (not melting up to 250°), sparingly soluble in mineral acids, freely in acetic acid and in absolute alcohol; insoluble in chloroform, benzene and ether. Dilute alcoholic solution effervesces slightly with a dilute solution of sodium bicarbonate.

The acetic acid solution dyes wool and silk a deep bluish-violet shade. (Found: N, 9.48. $C_{26}H_{23}O_3N_3$ requires N, 9.9 per cent.)

Tetra-p-hydroxytetraphenylmethane-o-carboxylic acid was prepared from (IX) (yield 70 per cent.) Dark brown microcrystalline powder (not melting up to 200°). Soluble in alkalis, ammonia and alcohol; insoluble in acid, benzene, ether and chloroform. The ammonium salt solution dyes wool and silk a light pink shade. (Found: C, 72.6; H, 4.9. $C_{26}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 72.9; H, 4.6 per cent.)

Tri-p-amino-o-hydroxytetraphenylmethane-m-carboxylic Acid (X).—It is prepared by condensing *p*-rosaniline base and *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid at 170° for 8 hours, subsequent operations being same as in (VIII). It is a violet microcrystalline powder (not melting up to 250°), soluble in mineral acids (dull violet solution), acetic acid (bluish-violet solution) and alcohol; produces bluish-violet shade on wool and silk from acetic acid bath; the shade obtained from mineral acid baths is much bluer. (Found: N, 9.89. $C_{26}H_{23}O_3N_3$ requires N, 9.9 per cent.)

Tri-p-hydroxy-o-hydroxytetraphenylmethane-m-carboxylic acid was prepared from the above. Dark brown microcrystalline powder, soluble in caustic alkalis, ammonia and alcohol; insoluble in chloroform, ether, benzene and acid. The ammonium salt solution dyes wool and silk a bright yellow shade. (Found: C, 72.6; H, 4.9. $C_{25}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 72.9; H, 4.6 per cent.)

Tri-p-amino-p-hydroxy-m-methyltetraphenylmethane-m-carboxylic Acid (XI).—It was prepared by condensing *p*-rosaniline base and *o*-cresotinic acid at 165° exactly as in (VIII) (yield 80 per cent.) It

formed shining violet crystalline powder (melting at 87° - 90°), soluble in mineral acids (greenish-blue solution), acetic acid (bluish-violet solution) and absolute alcohol (violet solution); insoluble in ether, benzene and chloroform.

It effervesces slightly with a dilute alcoholic solution of sodium bicarbonate; acetic acid bath dyes wool and silk a brilliant bluish-violet shade, the shade obtained from a mineral acid bath being much bluer. (Found: N, 10.1. $C_{27}H_{25}O_3N_3$ requires N, 9.6 per cent.).

Tetra-p-hydroxy-m-methyltetraphenylmethane-m-carboxylic acid, $(CO_2H)(OH)(Me) \cdot C_6H_2 \cdot C(C_6H_4 \cdot OH)_3$ was prepared from the above (yield 60 per cent.). It formed dark brown micro-crystalline powder (not melting up to 250°), soluble in alkalis, ammonia and alcohol; insoluble in chloroform, ether and benzene. The ammonium salt solution dyes wool and silk a light yellow shade. (Found: C, 73.00; H, 5.2. $C_{27}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 73.3; H, 4.98 per cent.).

Tri-p-amino-2:3:4-trihydroxytetraphenylmethane-o-carboxylic Acid (XII).—It was prepared by condensing *p*-rosaniline base and gallic acid at 179° for 8 hours, subsequent operations being same as in (VIII) (yield 70 per cent.). It formed reddish-violet micro-crystalline powder (not melting up to 250°), soluble in mineral acids, acetic acid, alcohol and acetone; insoluble in ether, benzene and chloroform; acetic acid bath dyes wool and silk a reddish-violet shade. (Found: N, 8.3. $C_{26}H_{23}N_3O_3$ requires N, 9.1 per cent.).

Tri-p-hydroxy-2:3:4-trihydroxytetraphenylmethane-o-carboxylic acid was prepared from the above by the diazo reaction (yield 60 per cent.). It formed dark brown micro-crystalline powder (not melting up to 250°), soluble in alkalies, ammonia and alcohol; insoluble in acids, ether, benzene and chloroform. The ammonium salt solution dyes wool and silk a straw yellow shade. (Found: C, 67.5; H, 4.7. $C_{26}H_{20}O_8$ requires C, 67.83; H, 4.35 per cent.).